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Virtual Energy Storage Stacking in Day-Ahead and mFRR markets – A Spanish Case Study

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Abstract

Addressing the imperative for climate action requires adaptable energy solutions. Leveraging distributed technology like Virtual Energy Storage Systems (VESSs), the i-STENTORE project aims to pioneer innovative solutions for the widespread deployment of energy storage systems. This paper explores the potential of VESSs to increase the revenue of different distributed renewable technologies in the Iberian Wholesale and manual Frequency Restoration Reserve (mFRR) markets. Research up to date has focused on several market integration aspect of VESSs, yet considering the intricacies of the Iberian market of these technologies remains unexplored. The research aims to provide real-world insights into the potential of VESSs to increase the revenue of these technologies by stacking different services in the Iberian market. The results will show the potential of this demonstrator to increase profits using the concept of VESS and several storage technologies into the Iberian market.

Index Terms

manual Frequency Restoration Reserve, Revenue Stacking, Virtual Battery Energy Storage System

I. INTRODUCTION

CONFRONTING the challenges posed by climate change involves utilizing electricity storage, which plays a pivotal role in enabling the next phase of the energy transition. By facilitating the integration of renewable energy sources, electricity storage emerges as a critical enabler for achieving sustainable energy systems. [1]. Despite advancements, challenges persist in cost-effectiveness and operational efficiency, motivating initiatives like i-STENTORE to pioneer storage solutions. The Granada demonstrator integrates an in-front-of-the-meter Li-ion battery (LIB) and a behind-the-meter Vanadium Redox Flow Battery (VRFB) to form a Virtual Energy Storage System (VESS). This system supports nearby renewable power plants, including a small wind power plant, a small PV plant, and a run-of-river hydro-power plant. It ensures optimal integration of renewable energy by coordinating the operation of all the assets. [2].

The evolving landscape of VESSs and their profound impact on power system operations and market dynamics can be seen through reference [3] which tackles the challenge of revenue maximisation through enabling flexible DERs to engage in multiple markets simultaneously, suggesting promising avenues for revenue optimization. This fact, coupled with the growing interest in demand response, underscores the significance of VESSs in providing frequency services while using multi-carrier energy storage systems [4], [5]. Moreover, the potential of VESS in providing ancillary services is underscored in [6], demonstrating its versatility and applicability across various domains. Exploring uncertainty management strategies in VESSs, [7] develops a risk-based control strategy for dispatching uncertain VESS, while authors in [8] proposes a data-driven optimization approach, enhancing economic operation and thermal comfort in uncertain environments. These innovative approaches offer promising solutions for mitigating uncertainty and improving the reliability of VESSs, but real-world applications remain scarce.

Deploying this VESS offers significant advantages, including cost-effectiveness by reducing capital and operational expenses to manage distributed generation [9], enhancing grid stability through real-time energy management [4], scalability by easily integrating additional geographically distributed resources [10], environmental benefits by reducing fossil fuel dependence and improving renewable integration, and better utilization of existing assets [11]. However, challenges include current complex regulatory frameworks, ensuring technical integration and real-time data management, mitigating cybersecurity risks while optimising assets, maintaining reliability and resilience of resources, and performing thorough cost-benefit analyses to ensure economic viability [6]. In this context, the practical utility and market potential of VESS are further investigated in [12], which delves into the market value of ESS in German energy markets, while [13] optimises revenue streams from grid-connected ESS in the PJM. Additionally, reference [14] provide economical insights into the aggregation of diverse DER technologies, while [15] introduces grid-scale VESS for enhancing renewable energy penetration for primary frequency response. Reference [16] proposes a clustering algorithm for VESS to enhance efficiency and increase household PV self-consumption, while [17] develops a control algorithm for heterogeneous VESS to optimise frequency containment reserve power. Reference [18] presents a bi-level decision-making strategy for DISCOs to enhance flexibility and manage congestion by integrating VESS into market participation plans.

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The existing literature has explored VESS for enhancing profits of Renewable resources in several markets and has investigated the impact of this technology to the distribution network. Yet there remains a research gap in addressing multi-step optimization for market participation in Wholesale and mFRR Iberian markets, particularly considering real-time corrections of the bids in the mFRR market, which constitutes the main contribution of this paper. The main novelty of this paper lies in examining the potential of VESSs consisting of a run-of-the-river hydro-power plant, alongside photovoltaic (PV) and wind turbine (WT) units, coupled with LIB and VRFB technologies to enhance profits in wholesale and mFRR markets. Given the type of the connection of the batteries, the VRFB will be mainly used for energy arbitrage in the wholesale market, while the LIB could be used to capitalise in both markets. While the VESS offers flexibility to the operation of the renewable assets, it necessitates a trade-off between the revenues and the degradation which is achieved by integrating a penalty term in the objective function. The findings highlight the system's capability to stack revenues without compromising the VESS performance.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section II describes the materials and methods used to evaluate the VESS at hand. Section III presents the results of the case study while Section IV concludes the paper.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A schematic of the VESS is shown in Fig. 1, where the interplay among the different energy flows is illustrated. Within the study's framework, the run-of-the-river hydro-power plant situated along the Monachil River in Granada epitomises a sustainable energy asset, using natural flow of water to generate electricity. Complementing this, the PV system and the WT system capitalises on solar and wind energy, respectively, to generate electricity. Due to its uncontrollable nature, these plants are subject to the wholesale market prices if no storage system is available. Thus, the VESS is designed to optimize the operation of these renewable assets, ensuring the most profitable operation in the Spanish market considering the size of the battery available.

As shown in Fig. 2, the Gate Opening Time (GOT) is settled at 11:00 while the Gate Closing Time (GCT) is set to 13:00 considering Operation Procedure 3.1. of the Spanish Day-Ahead Market. During this time the Market Representative upload the offer computed by the optimiser to be cleared. The results are published at 13:30 in the Basic Daily Program of Functioning. At that time the MR will communicate the VESS the cleared setpoints for the next day and the price of the energy imports/exports. With this information it is possible to compute the tertiary reserve available for the next day. Following the Operation Procedure 3.1., the VESS must offer all the available tertiary reserve for the next day. Nevertheless, Market Participants can modify their offers up to 25 min before the quarter-hourly period T . Given the size of the LIB of this demonstrator the VESS could participate in the tertiary reserve market using the offer type: "Scheduled Activation" in which the Transmission System Operator (TSO) will ask for the activation of maximum 15 minutes of tertiary reserve with 15 minutes of anticipation. Considering this restriction, the type of the link between offers is forced to be "Conditional", which enable retire the availability of the linked offer given the activation of offers up to two periods before.

A. Wholesale market participation

The participation of the VESS in the wholesale market is represented by (1). Let $t \in \Omega_t$ be the set of periods in the scheduling horizon, and $m \in \Omega_m$ be the set of segments for the degradation model of the Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs). Wholesale market prices are represented by λ_t^{DAM} , while the degradation cost of the LIB and VRFB are represented by $C_{\text{DEG}}^{\text{LIB}}$ and $C_{\text{DEG}}^{\text{VRFB}}$, respectively. P_t^{RE} represents the forecast of renewable energy production. η^{CH} and η^{DIS} are the mean charging and discharging efficiencies for the BESSs, respectively. Δt is the time step between periods, $\text{SOC}_0^{\text{LIB}}$ and $\text{SOC}_0^{\text{VRFB}}$ are the initial state of charge of the LIB and VRFB, respectively. \bar{P}^{LIB} and \bar{P}^{VRFB} are the power of the converter for the LIB and VRFB, respectively. State of charge limits are defined for the LIB and VRFB as $\underline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{LIB}}$, $\overline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{LIB}}$, $\underline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{VRFB}}$, and

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the VESS showcasing the interconnection between PV, WT, Li-ion and VRFB BESSs. Energy flows between the wholesale market and the VPP are represented by $p_t^{v,m}$ and $p_t^{m,v}$, between the VPP and the Li-ion BESS by $p_t^{v,l}$ and $p_t^{l,v}$, between the VPP and the VRFB BESS by $p_t^{v,s}$ and $p_t^{s,v}$. The energy produced by the PV, WT and the run-of-the-river hydro-power plant are represented by P_t^{RE} .

Figure 2. Time frame of the operation of the VESS in the Spanish market. Gate Opening Time for the Day-Ahead Market is at 11:00, while the Gate Closing Time is at 13:00. The results are published at 13:30. The VESS then computes the tertiary reserve available for the next day and submit it to the mFRR market between 21:00 and 23:00 of day D-1. On day D, the energy is delivered to the grid between 00:00 and 23:45.

$\overline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{VRFB}}$. Following the semi-empirical degradation model proposed by [19], the calendar and cyclic degradation for the LIB and VRFB are computed as $\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cal,LIB}}$, $\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cyc,LIB}}$, $\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cal,VRFB}}$, and $\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cyc,VRFB}}$. Binary variables z_t^{LIB} and z_t^{VRFB} indicates the charging or discharging status of the LIB and VRFB, and power flow variables $p_t^{v,m}$, $p_t^{v,l}$, $p_t^{v,s}$, $p_t^{m,v}$, $p_t^{l,v}$, $p_t^{s,v}$, representing power flow between the VESSs and the market.

$$\max \sum_t \lambda_t^{\text{DAM}} (p_t^{v,m} - p_t^{m,v}) - \sum_t C_{\text{DEG}}^{\text{LIB}} (\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cal,LIB}} + \Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cyc,LIB}}) - \sum_t C_{\text{DEG}}^{\text{VRFB}} (\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cal,VRFB}} + \Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cyc,VRFB}}) \quad (1a)$$

Subject to,

$$p_t^{v,m} + p_t^{v,l} + p_t^{v,s} = p_t^{m,v} + p_t^{l,v} + p_t^{s,v} + P_t^{\text{RE}} \quad \forall t \quad (1b)$$

$$\text{soc}_t^{\text{LIB}} = \text{soc}_{t-1}^{\text{LIB}} + \eta^{\text{CH}} p_t^{v,l} \Delta t - \frac{p_t^{l,v} \Delta t}{\eta^{\text{DIS}}} \quad \forall t > 1 \quad (1c)$$

$$\text{soc}_0^{\text{LIB}} = \text{SOC}_0^{\text{LIB}} \quad (1d)$$

$$\underline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{LIB}} \leq \text{soc}_t^{\text{LIB}} \leq \overline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{LIB}} \quad \forall t \quad (1e)$$

$$0 \leq p_t^{v,l} \leq z_t^{\text{LIB}} \overline{P}^{\text{LIB}} \quad \forall t \quad (1f)$$

$$0 \leq p_t^{l,v} \leq (1 - z_t^{\text{LIB}}) \overline{P}^{\text{LIB}} \quad \forall t \quad (1g)$$

$$\text{soc}_t^{\text{VRFB}} = \text{soc}_{t-1}^{\text{VRFB}} + \eta^{\text{CH}} p_t^{v,s} \Delta t - \frac{p_t^{s,v} \Delta t}{\eta^{\text{DIS}}} \quad \forall t > 1 \quad (1h)$$

$$\text{soc}_0^{\text{VRFB}} = \text{SOC}_0^{\text{VRFB}} \quad (1i)$$

$$\underline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{VRFB}} \leq \text{soc}_t^{\text{VRFB}} \leq \overline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{VRFB}} \quad \forall t \quad (1j)$$

$$0 \leq p_t^{v,s} \leq z_t^{\text{VRFB}} \overline{P}^{\text{VRFB}} \quad \forall t \quad (1k)$$

$$0 \leq p_t^{s,v} \leq (1 - z_t^{\text{VRFB}}) \overline{P}^{\text{VRFB}} \quad \forall t \quad (1l)$$

$$\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cal,LIB}} \geq a_m^{\text{LIB}} \text{soc}_t^{\text{LIB}} + b_m^{\text{LIB}} \quad \forall m, t \quad (1m)$$

$$\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cyc,LIB}} \geq c_m^{\text{LIB}} \left(\frac{p_t^{v,l} + p_t^{l,v}}{\overline{P}^{\text{LIB}}} \right) + d_m^{\text{LIB}} \quad \forall m, t \quad (1n)$$

$$\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cal,VRFB}} \geq a_m^{\text{VRFB}} \text{soc}_t^{\text{VRFB}} + b_m^{\text{VRFB}} \quad \forall m, t \quad (1o)$$

$$\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cyc,VRFB}} \geq c_m^{\text{VRFB}} \left(\frac{p_t^{v,s} + p_t^{s,v}}{\overline{P}^{\text{VRFB}}} \right) + d_m^{\text{VRFB}} \quad \forall m, t \quad (1p)$$

$$z_t^{\text{LIB}}, z_t^{\text{VRFB}} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall t \quad (1q)$$

The objective (1a) maximises the revenues obtained for the participation in the wholesale market while minimising the calendar and cyclic degradation for the LIB and VRFB. Energy balance of the VESS is ensured by (1b). State of charge update for the LIB is stated in (1c) and (1d), while (1e) set bounds for the SOC. The charging and discharging limits are enforced by (1f) and (1g) using z_t^{LIB} to indicate charging status. Similarly, equations (1h) to (1l) enforce the same operational constraints for the VRFB. Calendar and cyclic degradation for the LIB are computed in (1m) and (1n) for the LIB, and in (1o) and (1p) for the VRFB.

B. Iberian mFRR market participation

After the wholesale market operation set points are published at 13:30 ($p_t^{v,m*}$, $p_t^{v,l*}$, $p_t^{v,s*}$, $p_t^{m,v*}$, $p_t^{l,v*}$, $p_t^{s,v*}$) the VESS computes the availability of the LIB to provide tertiary reserve. The mFRR market participation is represented by (2). Let λ_t^u and λ_t^d be the prices for the mFRR services at time t , P^{MIN} , the minimum offer in the mFRR market, M , a big enough number

defined as $2\bar{P}^{\text{LIB}}$. Decision variables include z_t^{LIB} , binary variables indicating the charging (1) or discharging (0) status of the LIB, y_t^u and y_t^d , binary variables that ensure minimum bid requirements of the mFRR market in the upward and downward directions, $p_t^{\text{dis,u}}$ and $p_t^{\text{ch,u}}$, discharging and charging power of the LIB BESS contributing to the upward mFRR product, $p_t^{\text{dis,d}}$ and $p_t^{\text{ch,d}}$, discharging and charging power of the LIB BESS contributing to the downward mFRR product, $\text{soc}_t^{\text{mFRR}}$, the state of charge of the LIB at time t for the mFRR market.

$$\max \sum_t [\lambda_t^u (p_t^{\text{dis,u}} + p_t^{\text{ch,u}}) + \lambda_t^d (p_t^{\text{dis,d}} + p_t^{\text{ch,d}})] - \sum_t C_{\text{DEG}}^{\text{LIB}} (\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cal,LIB}} + \Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cyc,LIB}}) \quad (2a)$$

Subject to,

$$p_t^{v,l*} + p_t^{\text{ch,d}} - p_t^{\text{ch,u}} \leq \bar{P}^{\text{LIB}} z_t^{\text{LIB}} \quad \forall t \quad (2b)$$

$$p_t^{v,l*} + p_t^{\text{ch,d}} \leq \bar{P}^{\text{LIB}} z_t^{\text{LIB}} \quad \forall t \quad (2c)$$

$$p_t^{v,l*} - p_t^{\text{ch,u}} \geq 0 \quad \forall t \quad (2d)$$

$$p_t^{l,v*} + p_t^{\text{dis,u}} - p_t^{\text{dis,d}} \leq \bar{P}^{\text{LIB}} (1 - z_t^{\text{LIB}}) \quad \forall t \quad (2e)$$

$$p_t^{l,v*} + p_t^{\text{dis,u}} \leq \bar{P}^{\text{LIB}} (1 - z_t^{\text{LIB}}) \quad \forall t \quad (2f)$$

$$p_t^{l,v*} - p_t^{\text{dis,d}} \geq 0 \quad \forall t \quad (2g)$$

$$p_t^{\text{ch}} = p_t^{v,l*} + p_t^{\text{ch,d}} - p_t^{\text{ch,u}} \quad \forall t \quad (2h)$$

$$p_t^{\text{dis}} = p_t^{l,v*} + p_t^{\text{dis,u}} - p_t^{\text{dis,d}} \quad \forall t \quad (2i)$$

$$\text{soc}_t^{\text{mFRR}} = \text{soc}_{t-1}^{\text{mFRR}} + [\eta^{\text{CH}} \Delta t p_t^{\text{ch}} - \frac{\Delta t}{\eta^{\text{DIS}}} p_t^{\text{dis}}] \quad \forall t \quad (2j)$$

$$\text{SOC}_0^{\text{mFRR}} = \text{SOC}_0^{\text{mFRR}} \quad (2k)$$

$$\underline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{LIB}} \leq \text{soc}_t^{\text{mFRR}} \leq \overline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{LIB}} \quad \forall t \quad (2l)$$

$$p_t^{\text{ch,u}} + p_t^{\text{dis,u}} \geq P^{\text{MIN}} y_t^u \quad \forall t \quad (2m)$$

$$p_t^{\text{ch,u}} + p_t^{\text{dis,u}} \leq M y_t^u \quad \forall t \quad (2n)$$

$$p_t^{\text{ch,d}} + p_t^{\text{dis,d}} \geq P^{\text{MIN}} y_t^d \quad \forall t \quad (2o)$$

$$p_t^{\text{ch,d}} + p_t^{\text{dis,d}} \leq M y_t^d \quad \forall t \quad (2p)$$

$$\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cal,LIB}} \geq a_m^{\text{LIB}} \text{soc}_t^{\text{mFRR}} + b_m^{\text{LIB}} \quad \forall m, t \quad (2q)$$

$$\Delta b_{\text{loss},t}^{\text{cyc,LIB}} \geq c_m^{\text{LIB}} \left(\frac{p_t^{\text{ch}} + p_t^{\text{dis}}}{\bar{P}^{\text{LIB}}} \right) + d_m^{\text{LIB}} \quad \forall m, t \quad (2r)$$

The objective function (2a) maximizes the benefits from the participation in the mFRR, while minimizing the degradation of the LIB battery. Equations (2b) to (2i) ensure the operation of the LIB in the mFRR, avoiding simultaneous charging and discharging. Equations (2j) to (2l) update the SOC of the LIB after the market participation. Equations (2m) to (2p) ensure that the bid provided by the LIB complies with the minimum size set by the market P^{MIN} . Lastly, calendar and cyclic degradation are computed in equations (2q) and (2r), respectively. This problem needs to be solved every time there is an activation of the mFRR products for the remaining scheduling horizon.

C. Real-time mFRR corrections

Regarding the conditional links between the offers, given the limited size of the battery is analyzed in Table I and visualized in Fig. 3. Based on the activation of the upward and downward products in T-2 and T-1 periods, the submitted upward and downward offer at time T is enabled to be activated (YES) or disabled to be activated (NO) by the TSO.

Given this conditional linkage of the offers, the availability of tertiary reserves should be sequentially updated every time the TSO activates it, i.e. optimization problem (2) should be solved for each activation of the tertiary reserves fixing the variables of the previous periods.

D. Simulation algorithm

The simulation algorithm is built on a multi-step optimization approach, where the VESS operation is firstly optimised for the wholesale market, and then for the mFRR market on a day-ahead basis. The real-time corrections of the mFRR market is considered in the algorithm in real-time considering the conditional links between the offers and the information available at each moment. The algorithm is outlined in Algorithm 1.

Table I
EVALUATION OF THE POSSIBLE CONDITIONAL LINKS BETWEEN THE OFFERS GIVEN THE LIMITED SIZE OF THE BATTERY.

	Up Act. T-2	Up Act. T-1	Down Act. T-2	Down Act. T-1	Up Offer T	Down Offer T
1	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
2	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes
3	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
4	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
5	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
6	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
7	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes

Figure 3. Visualization of the conditional linking of the tertiary offers. Periods T-30 and T-15 influence in the availability of energy for period T since the total energy available is limited. The modification limit of the offers is 25 minutes before the quarter-hourly period T, and the SO call happens 15 min before the period T.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. System and Scenario Description

The Granada demonstrator integrates renewable assets including a WT of 4.2 MW and an annual yield exceeding 10 GWh, alongside a PV of 4 MWp and yielding approximately 6.8 GWh annually and a small run-of-the-river hydro-power plant of 2.4 MW. These renewable energy sources serve as the primary generation capacity for the system, providing the necessary energy input for the VESS operation and grid support services. Managed by MECSA, the local Distribution System Operator and Electricity Supply Company, the VESS coordinates storage services comprising a Li-ion BESS of 1 MW/0.5 MWh and a VRFB with 250 kW/625 kWh, connected to different nodes of the grid.

To control such a system, an Hierarchical Control System is used, which involves a multi-layer configuration to manage the operation of all the components of the VESS. At device level, each battery unit is equipped with Battery Management

Algorithm 1: Multi-step Wholesale and mFRR simulator.

```

1 begin
2   for  $d \in \mathcal{D}$  do
3     VESS Schedules  $\leftarrow$  Solve DAM (1)
4     VESS mFRR availability  $\leftarrow$  Solve mFRR (2)
5     for  $t \in \Omega_t = [1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{T} - 2]$  do
6        $p_t^{u,act}, p_t^{d,act} \leftarrow \text{Dir}(t), \text{Link}(t - 1, t - 2)$ 
7        $p_{t+1}^{u,act}, p_{t+1}^{d,act} \leftarrow \text{Dir}(t + 1), \text{Link}(t, t - 1)$ 
8        $p_{t+2}^{u,act}, p_{t+2}^{d,act} \leftarrow \text{Link}(t + 1, t)$ 
9        $p_t^{ch}, p_t^{dis}, soc_t^{RT} \leftarrow p_t^{u,act}, p_t^{d,act}$ 
10      if  $\|soc_t^{LIB} - soc_t^{RT}\| > 0$  then
11        for  $\tau = [1, 2, \dots, t + 2]$  do
12          Fix  $p_\tau^u, p_\tau^d \leftarrow p_\tau^{u,act}, p_\tau^{d,act}$ 
13        end
14         $p_t^u, p_t^d, soc_t^{LIB} \leftarrow$  Solve mFRR (2)
15      end
16    end
17    Log market participation results for day  $d$ 
18  end
19 end

```

Systems (BMS) to monitor the state of charge, temperature, and voltage of the cells. Locally, an Energy Management System (EMS) coordinates the renewable assets and storage, optimizing their operation based on real-time data and forecasts, while a SCADA system provides comprehensive monitoring and control. At the system level, a Virtual Power Plant (VPP) software aggregates the distributed energy resources for market participation, and a Distribution Management System (DMS) ensures reliability and quality of supply, interfacing with the VPP to align local operations with broader grid requirements.

To evaluate the system's performance, renewable energy profiles are obtained from historical data in 2022 [20]–[22]. Simulations are performed using Gurobi 9.5.1 [23] and Python 3.9.18 [24] on an Apple M1 Processor with 16 GB of RAM. The simulation for the wholesale market consider an hourly time resolution for the next three years, while the mFRR market considers a 15-minute time resolution for the next 24 hours. The total number of the continuous and binary variables is 672 and 288 for the wholesale market model, 1,056 and 192 for the mFRR market model. The number of constraints is 960 and 1,248 for the former and latter models, respectively. The solver takes less than one second to solve each problem considering a MIP gap of 5%.

B. Market Participation

The VESS operation in the wholesale market is shown in Fig. 4. This figure is drawn after step 3 of the simulation algorithm, where the VESS operation is optimized for the wholesale market. As it can be seen, the VESS storage as much energy as possible during the low price periods and discharges it during the high price periods, in this case in the LIB as the VRFB is fully charged.

Figure 4. VESS exchanges with wholesale market for one representative day of the simulation. (a) p_t^{VRFB} and p_t^{LIB} represent the charging (positive) and discharging (negative) powers for VRFB and LIB, respectively. (b) $p_t^{v,m}$ represents the power flow from the VESS to the market, while p_t^{RE} and λ_t^{DAM} represent the renewable energy production and the market price.

The VESS stack of products is shown in Fig. 5. The battery effectively provide energy arbitrage and mFRR services, capitalizing on the activation of the mFRR products, while providing previously compromised offers in the wholesale market in real-time. The profits obtained in the wholesale and mFRR markets for the year under study are 874.292 k€ and 14.695 k€, respectively. This results in a total profit of 888.987 k€ increasing the profits by 3.261% compared to the case without VESS, where the profits are only sold in the wholesale market without any possibility of energy arbitrage or mFRR services. In the latter case, the profits are 860.911 k€. During this year, the total degradation of the LIB and VRFB are 23.494 kWh and 4.991 kWh, respectively. The cost of degradation for the LIB and VRFB are 3.289 k€ and 0.998 k€, considering replacement costs of 140 and 200 €/kWh, respectively.

A more detailed operation of the VESS in the mFRR market is shown in Fig. 6. This figure is drawn after step 17 of the simulation algorithm, where the VESS operation is being optimised in real-time given the calls of the TSO, the direction of the event - which is unknown at step 4 of the algorithm - and the conditional links presented in Table I. This figure showcase how the VESS capitalize on the activation of the mFRR products, while providing previously compromised offers in the wholesale market in real-time, ensuring that the VESS can provide the required tertiary reserves by the TSO. It is possible to see that the VESS only effectively provides the mFRR services when the TSO activates the products in the direction where the VESS has energy available.

Figure 5. Stacking of mFRR and wholesale energy products for a typical day of operation. The LIB provide energy arbitrage services in the wholesale market (green and blue bars), while capitalizing the remaining power in the mFRR market (red and black bars).

Figure 6. Real-time corrections for the mFRR market. Filled black and red bars represent the activation of the upward $p_t^{u,*}$ and downward $p_t^{d,*}$ products, respectively. The bar with strips represent the offers submitted that were not activated in each direction. Blue and green bars represent the previously compromised offers in the charging $p_t^{v,l,*}$ and discharging $p_t^{l,v,*}$ directions in the wholesale market, respectively. Arrows over the bars indicate the final direction of the activated mFRR event.

IV. CONCLUSION

Confronting climate change requires effective electricity storage for renewable energy integration. The Granada demonstrator, part of the i-STENTORE project, integrates LIB and VRFB with renewable power plants. Existing VESS research lacks multi-step optimization for joint wholesale and mFRR market participation, which this paper addresses. It proposes a VESS comprising a run-of-the-river hydro-power plant, PV, and wind units, with Li-ion and VRFBs, enhancing profits in wholesale and mFRR markets. The paper presents models for wholesale and mFRR market participation, considering real-time corrections after the TSO activate the submitted availability. Results demonstrate revenue maximization, obtaining an increase in profits compared with the sole participation in wholesale markets, a 3.261 % for this case study. This research contributes to advancing renewable energy technologies and optimizing energy system sustainability. Future work will focus on the development of a real-time control strategy for the VESS, considering the stochastic nature of the renewable energy sources, the market prices, and the TSO calls.

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